

WONDERFUL MULTIMEDIA - APPLYING IN AREAS OUTSIDE OF TEACHING

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ANNOTATION. This article discusses the applying of multimedia - technologies in areas outside of teaching education.

Keywords: multimedia, multimedia technologies, multimedia resources, multimedia products, non-educational multimedia, multimedia teaching aids, multimedia information visualization.

INTRODUCTION

Modern society is characterized by certain changes associated with the introduction of information technology in all areas of education and science, production, management, business, culture. In information environments, the concepts of "multimedia", "multimedia technologies", "multimedia resources", "multimedia products", "educational multimedia", "multimedia learning tools", "multimedia information visualization", etc. are often used.

Consider the concept of "multimedia" in the application in areas not related to education, its distinctive features, what is its role and value for these purposes. We know that the term "multimedia" literally means "multi-media", "poly-environment", that is, content that is presented simultaneously in different forms: sound, animated computer graphics, video. Multimedia is considered a computer technology that allows the presentation of content through a combination of different types of information - both through traditional static information (text, graphics) and through dynamic information (animation, speech, music, video). Multimedia is a single digital space, syncretic representing different ways and types of information presentation.

Multimedia is classified as linear and non-linear. In linear representation, the viewer of a given document cannot influence its output in any way. In a non-linear (interactive) way of presenting information, a person can participate in the output of information by interacting in some way with the means of displaying multimedia data. This process is also called "interactivity". An example for this process is multimedia simulations. A non-linear way of representing multimedia data is sometimes referred to as "hypermedia".

As an example of a linear and non-linear way of presenting information, we can consider the situation associated with the presentation. In MS Power Point presentations, viewers do not have the ability to influence the presenter. In Prezi presentations, the audience has the opportunity to interact with it. Thus, a live presentation can be presented as a non-linear way of presenting information. It can be noted that various forms of providing information make it possible for the consumer to interact interactively with information. Online multimedia is increasingly becoming object-oriented, allowing the consumer to work on information without having specific knowledge.

RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

Multimedia finds its application in various fields such as programming, advertising, entertainment, technology, medicine, mathematics, business, scientific research, cartography, art and space-time applications.

Multimedia presentations can be made by a person on stage, shown through a projector, or on another local playback device. A broadcast presentation can be either live or pre-recorded. Broadcasting or recording can be based on analog or electronic technologies for storing and transmitting information. It is worth noting that online multimedia can either be downloaded to the user's computer and played in some way, or played directly from the Internet using data streaming technologies. Media played using streaming technologies can be either live or on-demand.

In the media, one key feature of new media is multimedia, that is, the ability to combine different formats within one publication. In fact, multimedia makes it possible to replace part of the text with visual elements, which makes it possible to attract and

hold the attention of today's multitasking, "distracted" user, and to make the perception of the material as easy as possible. Multimedia has led to the emergence of a separate direction in journalism - along with print, radio and television journalism, multimedia journalism has emerged. This type of journalism is a way of presenting journalistic material, a media product that is dedicated to one topic and combines several formats - photo, video, text, infographics, interactive.

In the field of Internet resources, an Internet multimedia resource is a site in which the main information is presented in the form of multimedia. This is a modern and very convenient mechanism that does not replace the performance of classical functions, but complements and expands the range of services and news for visitors. Multimedia Internet resources:

- may contain various types of information;
- have a high degree of clarity of materials;
- support various types of files;
- can be used to promote creative works in the field of various arts.

Entertainment and the visual arts use special effects and animation in the creation of films and computer games. Entertainment and art have so closely penetrated each other that a new genre has appeared - video games. Virtual reality surpasses material reality with events and colors. Genres are mixed in this parallel world. Exhibition galleries are an example. In multimedia games, the player interacts with a virtual environment built by the computer. The state of the virtual environment is transmitted to the player using various methods of information transfer (auditory, visual, tactile). Currently, all games on a computer or game console are multimedia games. It is worth noting that this type of games can be played alone on a local computer or console, or with other players via a local or global network.

The development of computer games with multimedia content belongs to the class of software systems of high complexity. Their development requires high qualification. Designing games as software systems requires the ability to analyze the requirements for a software system, programming skills, features of technical tools and development

environments. In addition, the implementation of computer games requires knowledge in the field of:

- development of algorithms;
- design and development of interactive applications, two-dimensional and three-dimensional computer graphics;
- cross-platform programming languages, etc.

The development process includes task analysis, development of game objects and animations, setting up physics and methods of user interaction with game objects, development of pathfinding algorithms and artificial intelligence (AI) elements, building game levels, building a user interface, debugging and testing the project.

In the advertising field, they are used together with traditional multimedia technologies (television) and the Internet. This combination is used in outdoor advertising to attract the attention of consumers. Industrial, business and intra-office communications are typically designed by creative services that develop modern multimedia presentations. Multimedia technologies are widely used in the design of outdoor advertising. With their help, effective information tablets, mobile streetlines, 3D steles and other complex structures are created.

In multimedia technology, they do an excellent job of simulating the most complex technological operations. Drivers and pilots who have completed virtual training can easily switch to real driving. Software developers can use multimedia in computer simulations for anything from entertainment to education, such as military or industrial training. Multimedia for APIs is often created as a collaboration between creative professionals and software developers. In the field of communication and communication, multimedia is used when sending a message MMS (Multimedia Messaging Service) - a function typical for modern mobile phones for sending and receiving multimedia messages. The specificity of the modern new electronic communication system is the culture of real virtuality, characterized by the global scale of its distribution and impact on all spheres of public life and human existence in general. The initial forms of communication to a certain extent paved the way for modern media communication analogues. Since the exchange of information is a

necessary component of the life of society, media technologies, as a mediating link in human activity, are one of the ways of communication, a condition for human activity.

It is possible to conditionally divide media technologies into five types:

- early (pre-literate types and script),
- printing (printing, lithography, photography),
- electrical (telegraph, telephone, sound recording),
- mass media (cinema, television, mass media),
- digital (computer, Internet).

The evolution in the field of multimedia is the result of the formation and development of each type of media and a new era, primarily electronic digital media (television and the Internet). It is they who create the technical possibility for creating a super-saturated information field that surrounds modern man almost everywhere.

In the industrial sector, multimedia is used as a way to present information to shareholders, management and colleagues. Multimedia is also useful in organizing staff training, advertising and product sales around the world through virtually unlimited web technologies. Multimedia technologies are actively involved in the design of cars and machines for various purposes. A modern engineer needs skills in CAD (Computer Aided Design) or CAE (Computer Aided Engineering). These technologies allow you to observe the product simultaneously from different angles of view, which greatly facilitates the analysis and elimination of deficiencies.

In mathematical and scientific research, multimedia is mainly used for modeling and simulation. For example: a scientist can look at the molecular model of a substance and manipulate it in order to obtain another substance. A scientist can easily manipulate the molecular model of a substance, achieving the required properties. Exemplary research can be found in journals such as the Journal of Multimedia.

In modern medicine, multimedia is used very often. The use of equipment in the field of multimedia for hospitals, clinics and hospitals is one of the leading trends in the healthcare sector, which has made it possible to bring medicine and general medicine to a new level of development. Doctors can be trained through virtual operations or simulations of a human body affected by a disease spread by viruses and

bacteria, thus trying to develop methods for its prevention. Multimedia technologies in medicine help to improve the prevention of these diseases. In all medical institutions today you can see various information display systems: displays, monitors, video walls, projection equipment. Depending on the room in which the display system is installed, its tasks may be different. For example, a display in the lobby of a clinic might show doctors' schedules, while a monitor in an operating room might show an image from medical equipment. Video conferencing systems are successfully used not only by medical management to discuss the development and management of a medical institution, but also by doctors themselves. For example, videoconferencing allows real-time discussion of complex clinical cases with colleagues located in another city or even country. Congress systems in assembly halls, conference rooms and meeting rooms of a hospital are used for business meetings, medical consultations and meetings. The equipment of the congress system ensures the convenience of communication for all participants, as well as additional features, such as automated voting.

Thanks to the introduction of innovations, it has become possible to carry out the most complex operations with a demonstration of the procedure on monitors, hold conferences and meetings with specialists from all over the world, and simplify patient registration through the use of an electronic recording system. In order to create an integrated information space in medical institutions, professional monitors with a slide-out and transformation mechanism, power-saving mode and viewing angle adjustment, plasma and LCD displays with Full HD resolution and backlight are used to demonstrate the smallest details of the image, improve the clarity and quality of the picture, multimedia, digital and analog congress systems with a user-friendly interface and privacy protection, optimal for scientific conferences and remote meetings, personal and group video conferencing units with echo and background noise suppression, high-definition image transmission and data recording capability, public address systems, loudspeakers and microphones necessary for organizing the reception of patients, informing staff and ensuring security, interactive equipment for navigating in the premises of medical institutions, informing about the composition of the meadow and electronic appointment.

CONCLUSIONS

Multimedia technologies every day more and more penetrate into various spheres of human activity. In most cases, the use of multimedia content has had a positive impact on the intensification of human labor. Multimedia tools are used to improve the process of activities. The use of multimedia content in the labor process raises it to a qualitatively new level, positively affects the motivation of a person to work, increases the level of their viability and activity in choosing methods for solving the tasks they face. These are not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of application to the process of activity. Due to the simultaneous impact of graphic, sound and visual information on a person, multimedia tools have a great emotional, spectacular charge. At the same time, thanks to the ability to visually, spectacularly present information, multimedia allows you to implement the fundamental principle of visibility at a qualitatively new level.

Multimedia is also actively used in information institutions, in business and advertising, in the entertainment and leisure industry, i.e. where it is necessary to efficiently transfer large amounts of information per unit of time. It can be concluded that in the conditions of the emerging information society, both the educational and cultural and social role of multimedia is increasing, the age of multimedia digital culture is coming, everything happens through a multimedia resource. In general, “the fundamental difference between the information society and the industrial one is that it has the main wealth of knowledge drawn from information multimedia resources in order to maximize the use of highly developed technology to meet the material and spiritual needs of society.

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